

Synthesis and Characterization of Some 4-on Azitidine Derivatives from azo-chef Compounds, Evaluation of Biological Activity and Study of their Dye Stability

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Abstract

In this study, some new compounds have been prepared including the reaction of diazonium salt of 1,4-phenylenediamine with 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde at (0-5)OC[2]. Then Schiff bases [2-10] were then synthesized through the reaction of the compound [2] with substituted aniline in absolute ethanol, and Schiff bases were converted into Azetidines [11-18] by the reaction with 2-amino benzoic acid in ethanol. The prepared compounds were characterized by color and melting point, FT-IR, UV-Vis spectral analysis. Some of the prepared compounds were identified by ¹H-NMR spectra and C.H.N analysis. The antibacterial activities were studied against different kinds of bacteria, in addition, the stability of prepared dyes which proved to be of high stability and bright colors were studied, in addition, the conformation of prepared compounds at the lower energy level was studied.

Keywords: Azitidine, azo-chef Compounds, Dye Stability

1. Introduction

dyes contain at least one Nitrogen-Nitrogen double bond (N=N); however, many different structures are possible^[1]. Mono azo dyes have only (N=N) double bonds, while diazo and triazo dyes contain two and three (N=N) double bonds, respectively. The azo groups are generally connected to benzene and naphthalene rings, but can also be attached to aromatic heterocyclics such as chloroquine^[2].

The development of new antimicrobial organic compounds might afford further opportunities for the treatment of diverse microorganism infections that uncountable folks worldwide affected^[3]. Conversely, heterocyclic Schiff bases are well known for human treatment when illnesses are affecting for a protracted time^[4]. For that reason, researchers and pharmaceuticals are synthesizing and studying Schiff bases that are one of the most significant synthetic usages in organic chemistry

which are used as an intermediate for the synthesis of different compounds [5] Schiff bases are known as imines or azomethines which had been discovered by Hugo Schiff in 1864 [6] The functional group of (C=N) is the functional group of Schiff base which are commonly synthesized through the condensation of active carbonyl groups and primary amines [7,8]. Symmetrical bis-azomethines (ArN=CH-Ar CH=N-Ar) have a similar synthetic mono Schiff base's pathway but by using the different molar ratio [9]. Schiff bases have broad variability applications in a medicinal field that possess a wide spectrum of biological activities such as antibacterial [10], antioxidant [11], antifungal [12], anti-inflammatory, analgesic, anticancer [13], antitumor [14], anticonvulsant antimalarial, anti-tubercular [15], and antidiuretic [16]. involved a crucial site in organic chemistry, it is four-membered heterocyclic amides [17,18]. The (N) atom is linked to the 2-carbon atom neighboring to the carbonyl so it is referred to as Azetidin-2-one. Staudinger had synthesized 2-Azetidinone in 1907 for the first time through [2+2] ketene-imine cycloaddition reaction [15]. Azetidin-2-one is based on the varieties of the important antibiotics on an individual basis human and varied medicines [19]. Azetidin-2-one antibiotic action by inhibiting the microorganism cytomembrane in each gram-positive and gram-negative microorganism caused by their sturdy binding affinity to energetic penicillin-binding proteins (PBPs) [20]. To date, researchers still improvements and discovering new drugs as a result of vying a vital role in the therapeutic field owing to their broader spectrum of biological activities [21] such antibacterial, antifungal [22], antioxidant [11], anticancer, analgesic and antiviral activities [23], anti-inflammatory [4], antimalarial [24]. In a read of that overhead biotic importance, the current study has been focused on the synthesis of the Bis-Schiff bases and their 2-Azetidinone. All the synthesized

compounds were tested for antibacterial activities

2. Materials

All chemicals were Commercially supplied and used without further Purification

Physical Measurements

Melting Points were obtained on Electro thermal 9300 and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on FTIR 8400si Shimadzu spectrometer in the range 400-4000 cm^{-1} as KBr disc. Electronic spectra were measured between 200-400 nm with 10^{-3}M solutions in DMSO Solvent (spectroscopic grade) at 25°C using Shimadzu, UV-Vis 1800PC spectrophotometer. NMR spectra (^1H and $^{13}\text{C}\{-^1\text{H}\}$ NMR) were Performed in DMSO- d_6 solutions using Brukeravance 400 MHz spectrometers Chemical shifts are expressed in parts per million downfield from tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal standard.

Synthesis of Azo Compounds

Azo compounds are synthesized by depending on the method reported by Jarrahpour and Zarei [25]. There are two steps in the synthesis of azo compounds:

Step I: Diazotization: 1- Dissolve (0.02 mol, 3.684 gm) of 2-amino pyrimidin in a Erlenmeyer flask in (30 ml acid solution of 37% HCl (20 ml distilled water + 10 ml HCl) at a temperature of (0 - 5 °C) with constant stirring.

2- Dissolve in a second Erlenmeyer flask (0.04 mol, 2.76 gm) of NaNO_2 in the least possible amount of distilled water (4 ml), then add it to the solution of the first flask at a temperature (0-5 °C) and with stirring and the addition is gradual and in the form of drops The color change is evidence of the formation of diazanium salt, which was kept at (0-5 °C).

Step II: Coupling: Dissolve ((0.04 mol, 4.2 ml of salicylaldehyde in 30 ml) of pyridine at a temperature of 0 - 50 C) and after complete dissolution by continuous stirring, the diazonium salt prepared in the first step was added to it with stirring for one hour and it was confirmed that the reaction had finished Using TLC technique, and then poured the product into a beaker containing ice grits, so the precipitate was formed, then filtered, collected and left to dry until stable weight and recrystallized with ethanol, and the physical properties of the azo dye are shown in Table (1). Azo compounds are synthesized by depending on Scheme 1.

Synthesis of Schiff bases(3-10)^[26]

A series of Schiff bases (2-10) were prepared from the reaction of trimethoprim (0.01mol) with different aromatic amines (0.01mol) in 25 ml DMF or absolute ethanol and few drops of glacial acetic acid. This mixture was refluxed for 5hrs. The precipitate was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol. Melting points, yield% data are listed in Table (1).

Schiff bases compounds are synthesized by depending on Scheme 1.

Synthesis of azitidine derivatives 4-one (11-18)^[27]

(0.002 mol, 0.55 gm) of 2-chloroacetyl chloride mixed with (0.002 mol) of the prepared Schiff's bases [2-10] in (20 ml) 1,4-dioxane and (4ml) of triethylamine, and stirred for (20-24 hr.). The solvent evaporated and then treated and the formed precipitate was collected and recrystallized from mixture of (benzene – petroleum ether). Physical properties, yield and R_f are given in Table (2).

Dyeing processes^[28]

Dyeing was done for cotton and wool by dissolving prepared compounds [3-18] in ethanol, then the cotton and wool were dried at (50°C) for one hour. Washing was done with distilled water, and dried again, washed with sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl), and then dried. The stability of prepared pigments and the dyes proved high stability and bright colors.

Table (1):Physical properties data&(C.H.N)for newly manufactured Schiff bases azo dyes (3-10)

Sr. No.	Ar	Molecule formal/ Molecule weight	M.P. °C	Yield %	Colour	Found /(Cal.)		
						C%	H%	N%
3.		C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₆ O ₃ 348.32	224-226	86	Dark red	58.62 (58.51)	3.47 (3.37)	24.13 (24.17)
4.		C ₁₇ H ₁₂ ClN ₅ O 337.77	234-236	78	red	60.45 (60.01)	3.58 (3.58)	20.73 (20.73)
5.		C ₁₇ H ₁₂ BrN ₅ O 382.22	240-242	87	Dark red	53.42 (53.39)	3.16 (3.19)	18.32 (18.37)
6.		C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₅ O 317.35	265-267	74	Dark red	68.13 (68.19)	4.76 (4.79)	22.07 (22.1)
7.		C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₆ O 304.31	239-241	79	Dark red	63.15 (63.19)	3.97 (4.01)	27.62 (27.66)
8.		C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₇ O 305.30	218-220	80	red	59.06 (59.01)	3.63 (3.66)	32.12 (32.14)
9.		C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₅ O 303.33	244-246	88	red	67.32 (67.37)	4.32 (4.31)	23.09 (23.06)
10.		C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₆ O 304.31	221-223	74	Dark red	63.15 (63.19)	3.97 (4.01)	27.62 (27.66)

Table (1):Physical properties data&(C.H.N)for newly manufactured azo dyes (11-18)

Sr. No.	Ar	Molecule formal/ Molecule weight	M.P. °C	Yield %	Colour	Found /(Cal.)		
						C%	H%	N%
11.		C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ClN ₆ O ₄ 424.80	274- 276	77	Dark red	53.72 (53.51)	3.08 (3.07)	19.78 (19.67)
12.		C ₁₉ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₅ O ₂ 414.25	284- 286	81	red	55.09 (55.01)	3.16 (3.18)	16.91 (16.73)
13.		C ₁₉ H ₁₃ BrClN ₅ O ₂ 458.70	260- 262	66	Dark red	49.75 (49.39)	2.86 (3.89)	15.27 (15.37)
14.		C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ClN ₅ O ₂ 393.83	285- 287	62	Dark red	61.00 (61.19)	4.10 (4.79)	17.78 (17.1)
15.		C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClN ₆ O ₂ 380.79	279- 271	76	Dark red	56.78 (56.19)	3.44 (4.31)	22.07 (22.66)
16.		C ₁₇ H ₁₂ ClN ₇ O ₂ 381.78	248- 250	67	red	53.48 (53.01)	3.17 (3.66)	25.68 (25.14)
17.		C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ClN ₅ O ₂ 379.80	264- 266	71	red	60.09 (60.37)	3.72 (4.31)	18.44 (18.06)
18.		C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClN ₆ O ₂ 380.79	279- 271	76	Dark red	56.78 (56.19)	3.44 (4.31)	22.07 (22.66)

3. Results and Discussion

In this research, many compounds were prepared including azo, Schiff bases, and 2-Azetidinone, as in the following Scheme:

Scheme 1: Overall reaction steps

Azo dye[2] was prepared by the reaction diazonium salt of 2-amino pyrimidine with 2-hydroxy benzaldehyde at (0-5) °C. U.V-Vis. and FT IR Spectrum of azo dye are given in table (3), fig. (1a,1b), the ¹H-NMR and ¹³C-NMR spectrum of compound [2] is given in fig. (2a,2b).

The Schiff bases [3-10] were prepared by the compound [1] reaction with substitutes aniline in absolute ethanol. The prepared compounds were characterized by FT-IR, ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR, UV-Vis. Spectra. The UV spectra showed the transitions $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ which have confirmed the presence of the unbounded electrons pair on Nitrogen, oxygen atoms, and aromatic system (double bond) see fig (3,4).

The FT-IR spectrum for Schiff bases showed the disappearance of two bands

due to amino group, besides new bands which appear at (1649-1676) cm⁻¹ attributed to the azomethine (C=N) more than the appearance of the band at (1473-1541) cm⁻¹, and (1513-1587) cm⁻¹ due to (C=C) aromatic, and at (3400-3500) cm⁻¹ attributed to (OH) and at (1440-1460) cm⁻¹ attributed to (N=N). In addition, a band at (3040-3091) cm⁻¹ attributed to (C-H) aromatic, as shown in fig (5). U.V and FT-IR Spectrum were given in table (3). ¹H-NMR spectrum of compounds[3,4] was given in table (5) and fig. (6,7). ¹³C-NMR spectrum of compound [8] was given in table (4) and Fig. (8). The heat of formation for prepared compounds [3-10] were given in table (5). The steric conformation of compound [3-10] were studied in lower energy level using Chem office (2016) see fig (9-11).

Azitiidine 4-one derivatives [11-18] were prepared from the reaction of 2-

chloroacetyl chloride with Schiff bases [3-10] in 1,4-dioxane. The UV-Vis. spectra showed the transitions $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ which have confirmed the presence of the unbonded electrons pair on Nitrogen, Oxygen atoms and aromatic system (double bond) see fig (12,13).

The FT-IR spectrum showed a bands at (3400-3600) cm^{-1} due to (OH), and at (1652-1693) cm^{-1} due to (C=O) for imide compounds, respectively. Besides other bands at (1503-1564) cm^{-1} and at (1568-1598) cm^{-1} due to (C=C) aromatic ring, and at (3065-3084) cm^{-1} for aromatic (C-H), ,beside which appear bands at (1440-

1460) cm^{-1} due to (N=N) and at (2925-2968, 2810-2890) cm^{-1} due to (C-H) aliphatic and band at (1112-1190) cm^{-1} due to (C-N)beside which appear bands at (815-860) cm^{-1} due to (C-Cl). U.V. and FT-IR spectrum were given in table (3) see fig (11). $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of compound [14,16] was given in table (5) and Fig. (14,15). $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectrum of compound [12] was given in table (4) and Fig. (16). The heat of formation for prepared compounds [11-18] were given in table (7). The steric conformation of compound [11-18] were studied in lower energy level using Chem office (2016) see fig (17-19).

Table (3): FT-IR and UV/Vis data of the azo dye and Schiff bases Azitidine 4-one derivatives [2-18]

Com p. No.	$\lambda_{\max 1}$ $\lambda_{\max 2}$ EtOH nm	Ar	IR (KBr) cm^{-1}					
			ν (C-H) ν Arom. ν Aliph. sym /asy	ν (O H)	ν C=N)(ν N=N)(	ν (C=C) Arom. sym /asy	ν (C-N) ν (C-Cl)	Others
2.	261 391	-	3053 2806 2941	3400	----- 1452	1601 1612	1291 -----	-----
3.	261 393		3053 2806 2941	3470	1625 1452	1552 1610	1298 -----	Smy) 1343 ν (NO ₂ ν (Asmy) 1577
4.	227 322		3010 2899 2945	3508	1624 1450	1575 1585	1293 -----	(792) ν (C- Cl)
5.	227 322		3032 2890 2960	3400	1620 1440	1594 1603	1289 -----	(933) ν (C- Br)
6.	217 322		3066 2823 2935	3547	1622 1430	1557 1610	1288 -----	-----
7.	239 305		3041 2898 2927	3470	1630 1442	1577 1608	1291 -----	-----
8.	242 317		3070 2880 2990	3506	1624 1441	1609 1612	1287 -----	1646 ν (C=N)
9.	217 370		3032 2890 2960	3490	1625 1454	1599 1607	1283 -----	-----
10.	227 390		3032 2890 2960	3640	1622 1448	1590 1607	1286 -----	1640 ν (C=N)
11.	261 393		3053 2806 2941	3470	----- 1452	1553 1610	1280 820	Smy) 1353 ν (NO ₂ ν (Asmy) 1577
12.	227 322		3010 2899 2945	3508	----- 1450	1570 1585	1289 817	(840) ν (C- Cl)
13.	227 322		3032 2890 2960	3600	----- 1448	1595 1607	1290 830	(933) ν (C- Br)
14.	217 322		3062 2823 2935	3547	----- 1447	1556 1610	1297 840	-----
15.	239 305		3031 2894 2947	3470	----- 1442	1576 1608	1293 825	-----
16.	242 317		3075 2883 2950	3600	----- 1444	1603 1612	1292 822	1643 ν (C=N)
17.	217 370		3032 2820 2960	3490	----- 1440	1583 1607	1296 819	-----
18.	227 390		3032 2820 2940	3600	----- 1440	1589 1607	1299 816	1640 ν (C=N)

Table (4): ^1H , ^{13}C -NMR spectra azo dye and Schiff bases Azitidine 4-one derivatives [2, 4,7,8,12,14,16]

NO.	Tape	Data ppm
2	^1H -NMR	^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) 2.51 δH = 14.22(1H,s,OH) 9.45(1H,s,N=CH), 8.94-9.08(2H,dd,C-H-Pm.), 7.52-7.90(1H,t,C-H- Py.), 7.14-7.27 (1H,d,C-H-arom)., 6.70-6.69(1H,d,C-H-arom), 6.60(1H,s,C-H-arom).
2	^{13}C -NMR	^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6 Solvents(41.25)) δ 192.37(C16), 165.34(C1), 160.88(C13), 153.75(C4,C6), 145.32(C9), 130.87(C11), 122.95(C12), 119.74(C10), 118.40(C5), 105.98(C14),
3	^1H -NMR	^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) 2.51 δH = 13.22(1H,s,OH) 9.45(1H,s,N=CH), 8.94-9.08(2H,dd,C-H-Pm.), 7.52-7.90(1H,t,C-H- Py.), 7.14-7.27 (1H,d,C-H-arom)., 6.60-6.69(1H,d,C-H-arom), 6.60(1H,s,C-H-arom).
4	^1H -NMR	^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) 2.51 δH = 15.30(1H,s,OH) 9.45(1H,s,N=CH), 8.94-9.08(2H,dd,C-H-Pm.), 7.52-7.90(1H,t,C-H- Py.), 7.14-7.27 (1H,d,C-H-arom)., 6.70-6.69(1H,d,C-H-arom), 6.60(1H,s,C-H-arom).
8	^{13}C -NMR	^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6 Solvents(41.25)) δ 165.34(C1), 161.87(C18), 159.28(C13), 156.75(C16) , 153.38(C20,C22) , 150.30(C4,C6), 144.19(C9), 131.73(C11), 124.61(C12), 122.09(C10), 118.40(C5), 116.19(C21), 107.43(C14) .
12	^{13}C -NMR	^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6 Solvents (41.25)) δ 176.22(C13), 165.34(C1), 159.63(C26)(C4,6), 153.75(C9), 142.83(C18), 138.69(C21), 134.14(C11), 130.79(C20,22), 128.76(C19,23), 122.87(C10), 119.92(C12), 118.67(C5), 114.60(C14), 107.75(C16), 64.82(C25),
13	^1H -NMR	^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) 2.51 δH = 14.22(1H,s,OH) 9.45(1H,s,N=CH), 8.94-9.08(2H,dd,C-H-Pm.), 7.52-7.90(1H,t,C-H- Py.), 7.14-7.27 (1H,d,C-H-arom)., 6.70-6.69(1H,d,C-H-arom), 6.60(1H,s,C-H-arom).
15	^1H -NMR	^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) 2.51 δH = 14.22(1H,s,OH) 9.45(1H,s,N=CH), 8.94-9.08(2H,dd,C-H-Pm.), 7.52-7.90(1H,t,C-H- Py.), 7.14-7.27 (1H,d,C-H-arom)., 6.70-6.69(1H,d,C-H-arom), 6.60(1H,s,C-H-arom).

Table (5): Heat of formation of prepared compounds [2-18].

Comp. No.	Heat of Formation KJ/ mole	Comp. No.	Heat of Formation KJ/ mole
2.	484.93	11.	787.05
3.	744	12.	834.93
4.	834.93	13.	402.70
5.	702.91	14.	834.92
6.	196.35	15.	196.35
7.	888.10	16.	484.93
8.	787.05	17.	888.10
9.	757.33	18.	864.65
10.	196.35		

Dyeing process:

The resulting new dyes were highly colored and proven, as these dyes have thermal stability in which temperatures exceeded 100 °C, It was characterized by bright colors and showed clear consistency when washed with distilled water and

dried, and then washed with sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl). This is due to the length of the double bonds sequence resulted from the large structural formulas of the prepared compounds, as shown in fig. (6,7).

5-Determination of antibacterial activity^(28,29).

The result of antibacterial activity of Schiff Base and Azitidine 4-one derivatives [2, 4, 6, 9, 12, 15] are given in Table(6) and are against two types of bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (gram-negative) and *staphylococcus aureus* (gram-positive). The compounds were evaluated in vitro for their antibacterial activity against the tested bacteria by disc diffusion method the bacterial species. Nutrient agar was used for bacterial screening, DMSO was used as a solvent, Ampicillin, and Amoxicillin ($1 \times 10^{-1}, 1 \times 10^{-2}$ g/ml) as controls.

The agar well diffusion method was used to detect antibacterial activity compounds Schiff base and tetrazole derivatives of against two pathogenic bacteria species used in the present study as described by Barefoot and Klaenhammer. Young bacterial cultures suspension equivalent of

0.5 tube McFarland turbidity standards (108 cfu/ml) were spread on Muller-Hinton agar plates using sterile cotton swabs Wells of 6mm diameter were cut in solidified agar and filled with 50 μ l of each concentration. Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) is also used as a control. The plates were incubated aerobically at 37°C for 24 hours, then inhibition zones diameter (mm) around wells was measured by rule. All tests were applied in triplicate.

The antibacterial activity of the synthesized compounds [2, 4, 6, 9, 12, 15] were examined by the agar diffusion method using two different bacterial species, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The results indicated that some of the assayed compounds showed a microbial activity against the used bacteria. Antibacterial activity of compounds [2, 4, 6, 9, 12, 15]. Evaluation of the inhibitory activity of compounds prepared is given in fig. (17-20).

Table 6- Growth inhibition zone diameter(mm)of six heterocyclic compounds against two pathogenic bacteria species

Heterocyclic Compounds	Concentration (μ g/50 μ l)	Mean of Growth Inhibition Zone Diameter (mm)	
		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
2	1×10^{-1}	32	33
	1×10^{-2}	30	29
4	1×10^{-1}	29	34
	1×10^{-2}	27	29
6	1×10^{-1}	42	42
	1×10^{-2}	32	32
9	1×10^{-1}	35	40
	1×10^{-2}	22	22
12	1×10^{-1}	18	21
	1×10^{-2}	18	18
15	1×10^{-1}	18	17
	1×10^{-2}	17	17
DMSO (Control)	0.0	0.0	0.0
Amoxicillin	25	44	23
Ampicillin	25	38	50

Fig. (1a): The absorption spectrum for compound 2

Fig. (1b) Infrared spectrum of compound 2

Fig.(2a) ¹H-NMR spectrum the compound [2]

Fig. (2b) ¹³C-¹H}NMR spectrum of the compound [2]

Fig. (3): The absorption spectrum for compound 7

Fig. (4): The absorption spectrum for compound 5

Fig. (5) Infrared spectrum of compound 6

Fig.(6) ¹H-NMR spectrum the compound [3]

Fig.(7) ¹H-NMR spectrum the compound [4]

Fig. (8) ¹³C-¹H}NMR spectrum of the compound [8]

Fig. (9):Minimize energy conformation of compound11

Fig. (10):Minimize energy conformation of compound11

Fig. (11):Minimize energy conformation of compound11

Fig. (13): The absorption spectrum for compound 17

Fig. (12): The absorption spectrum for compound 13

Fig.(14) ¹H-NMR spectrum the compound [1]

Fig.(15) ¹H-NMR spectrum the compound [15]

Fig. (16) ¹³C-{¹H}NMR spectrum of the compound [12]

Fig. (17):Minimize energy conformation of compound 16

Fig. (18):Minimize energy conformation of compound 17

Fig. (19):Minimize energy conformation of compound 18

Fig. (6): Cotton dyeing pictures of compound 2,5,7,14,15

Fig. (18) The inhibitory activity of the compound [2,4₁] against bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* & *staphylococcus aureus*

Fig. (17) The inhibitory activity of the compound [6,9] against bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* & *staphylococcus aureus*

Fig. (17) The inhibitory activity of the compound [12,15] against bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* & *staphylococcus aureus*

4. References

- [1]. Hao, O.J. and Chang, P.C. (2000). Decolourization of waste water. *Critical Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol.*, (30): 449-505.
- [2]. Venkataraman, K. (1970). *The Chemistry of Synthetic Dyes*. New York and London: Academic Press.
- [3]. Kumar, S., Lim, S. M., Ramasamy, K., Vasudevan, M., Shah, S. A. A., Selvaraj, M., & Narasimhan, B. (2017). Synthesis, molecular docking and biological evaluation of bis-pyrimidine Schiff base derivatives. *Chemistry Central Journal*, 11(1), 1-16.
- [4]. Azzawi, A., & Al-Obiadi, K. K. (2016). Synthesis and anti-microbial screening of new bis-schiff bases and their acetyl oxadiazole azetidinone derivatives derived from pyromellitic diimide. *Int. J. Res. Pharm. Chem*, 6, 1-8.
- [5]. Ali, a., ghanim, H. T., & Said, M. H. (2015). Synthesis and identification of Schiff bases ligands as derivatives for terephthaldehyde and studies its complexes with some elemintes. *Journal of Applied, Physical and Biochemistry Research*, 1 (1), 9-16.
- [6]. Ayyash, A. N. (2019). A Novel Bioactive Compounds of 2-Azetidinone Derived from Pyrazin Dicarboxylic Acid: Synthesis and Antmicrobial Screening. *Journal of Acta Pharmaceutica Scientia*, 57 (4), 103-114.
- [7]. Bhuyar, S. S., Juneja, H. D., & PAIWAL, L. (2013). Synthesis, spectroscopic and thermal studies of newly synthesized transition metal coordination polymers. *Journal of Pharmaceutical*,

- Biological and Chemical Sciences. Research Res*, 20(4), 557-564.
- [8]. Sharma, R., Samadhiya, P., Srivastava, S. D., & Srivastava, S. K. (2012). Synthesis and pharmaceutical importance of 2-azetidinone derivatives of phenothiazine. *Journal of Chemical Sciences*, 124(3), 633-637.
- [9]. Güngör, Ö. Ö. (2017). Intramolecular proton transfer equilibrium in salicylidene-and naphthalene-based tetraimine Schiff bases. *Gazi University Journal of Science*, 30(1), 191-214.
- [10]. Ziwar, J. B., & MUSHEER, N. (2016). Synthesis of some Heterocyclic Compounds (Oxazepine, Diazepine) using Ultrasound Irradiation. *ZANCO Journal of Pure And Applied Sciences*, 28(2), 235-239.
- [11]. Hassan, S. A. (2019). Synthesis, Spectroscopic study and Biological activity of some New Heterocyclic compounds derived from Sulfadiazine. *Zanco Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 31(6), 92-109.
- [12]. Noori, n. S., Zaidan, t. A. & mesher, m. F. 2019. Synthesis and characterization of new complexes for (1e,1'e)-n,n'-(thiobis (4,1-phenylene)) bis(1-phenylmethanimine) substituted ligands with Fe^{3+} . *International research journal of pharmacy*, 9 (12), 57-63.
- [13]. Kajal, A., Bala, S., Kamboj, S., Sharma, N., & Saini, V. (2013). Schiff bases: a versatile pharmacophore. *Journal of Catalysts*, 2013. (3), 1-15.
- [14]. Ibrahim, A. R. (2015). Preparation and Characterization of some transition metal complexes of bis Schiff Base Ligand. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 8(3), 315-324.
- [15]. Khdur, R. A., & Zimam, E. H. (2018). Synthesis and characterization of some new β -lactam derivatives from azo sulphadiazine and its biological evaluation as anticancer. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*, 34(1), 371.
- [16]. Al-Masoudi, W. A., Faaz, R. A., Al-Asadi, R. H., & Jabbar, H. S. (2016). Synthesis, antimicrobial activity and modelling studies of some new metal complexes of Schiff base derived from sulphonamide drug in vitro. *European Journal of Chemistry*, 7(1), 102-106.
- [17]. Singh, M., Hazra, A., Bharitkar, Y. P., Kalia, R., Sahoo, A., Saha, S., ... & Mondal, N. B. (2018). Synthesis of diversely substituted bis-pyrrolizidino/thiopyrrolizidino oxindolo/acenaphthylene curcuminoids via sequential azomethine ylide cycloaddition. *RSC advances*, 8(34), 18938-18951.
- [18]. Hassan, S. A., & Aziz, D. M. (2021). Synthesis, in vitro Antimicrobial assay and Molecular Docking Studies of some new Symmetrical Bis-Schiff Bases and their 2-Azetidinones. *Zanco Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 33(2), 34-50.
- [19]. Singh, G. S., & Sudheesh, S. (2014). Advances in synthesis of monocyclic beta-lactams. *Arkivoc*, 1, 337-385.
- [20]. Piens, N. (2017). *Synthesis of new β -lactam building blocks and their application in heterocyclic chemistry* (Doctoral dissertation, Ghent University).
- [21]. Jurčík, V., Slawin, A. M., & O'Hagan, D. (2011). Single enantiomer synthesis of α -(trifluoromethyl)- β -lactam. *Beilstein journal of organic chemistry*, 7(1), 759-766.
- [22]. Mehta, P. D., Sengar, N. P., Subrahmanyam, E. V., & Satyanarayana, D. (2006). Synthesis and biological activity studies of some thiazolidinones and azetidinones. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 68(1), 103.
- [23]. Hassan, S. A., & Aziz, D. M. (2021). Synthesis, in vitro Antimicrobial assay and Molecular Docking Studies of some new Symmetrical Bis-Schiff Bases and their 2-Azetidinones. *Zanco Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 33(2), 34-50.
- [24]. Borazjani, N., Behzadi, M., Dadkhah Aseman, M., Jarrahpour, A., Rad, J. A., Kianpour, S., ... & Turos, E. (2020). Cytotoxicity, anticancer, and antioxidant properties of mono and bis-naphthalimido β -lactam conjugates. *Medicinal Chemistry Research*, 29, 1355-1375.
- [25]. Jarrahpour, A. A., & Zarei, M. (2004). Synthesis of novel azo Schiff base bis [5-(4-methoxyphenylazo)-2-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde]-1, 2-phenylene diimine. *Molbank*, 2004(1), M377.
- [26]. A Yass, I. (2010). Synthesis of substituted 1, 3-Oxazepine and 1, 3-Diazepine Via Schiff Bases for Selfamethoxazole drug. *karbala journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 1(1), 49-58.
- [27]. Ramachandran, S., Vimeshya, N., Yogeshwaran, K., Cheriyar, B. V., & Aanandhi, M. V. (2021). Molecular docking studies, synthesis, characterisation, and evaluation of azetidine-2-one derivative. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*, 14(3), 1571-1575.

- [28]. Mitra, S. (1984). Macromolecular Dyes— Synthetic Strategies. In *New Monomers and Polymers* (pp. 185-200). Springer, Boston, MA. Dalaf, A. H., & Jumaa, F. H. (2020). Synthesis, Identification and Assess the Biological and Laser Efficacy of New Compounds of Azetidine Derived from Benzidine. *AL-Muthanna Journal of Pure Sciences (MJPS)*, 7(2)12-25.
- [29]. Dalaf, A. H., Jumaa, F. H., & Salih, H.K.(2021). Preparation ,Characterization ,Biological Evaluation and Assess Laser Efficacy For New Derivatives of Imidazolidin-4-One, *International Research Journal of Multidisciplinary Technovation*, 3(4),41-51.